

COMPLEX MODEL OF THE UNIVERSE

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Abstract. We study unified theory with gauge group $SU(11)$. The subgroup $SU(6)$ has been interpreted as a new type of energy source other than $SU(5)$. We consider a $(4 + D)$ -dimensional Friedmann-Robertson-Walker type Universe having complex scale factor $R + iR_I$, where R is the scale factor corresponding to the usual 4-dimensional Universe while R_I is that of D -dimensional space. It is then compared with $(4+D)$ -dimensional Kaluza-Klein Cosmology having two scale factors R and $a (= iR_I)$. It is shown that the rate of compactification of higher dimension depends on extra dimension ' D '. The Wheeler-DeWitt equation and general solution is obtained. It is found that for $D = 6$ (i.e. in 10 dimension), the Wheeler-DeWitt equation is symmetric under the exchange $R_I \leftrightarrow R$.

1. Introduction. One of the exciting discoveries of 20th century is the unified theory of the fields. A natural query is what happened before unification—may be called super unified field. According to modern quantum field theory, the structure of a vacuum turns out to be interrelated with some spontaneous symmetry-breaking effects through the condensation of quantum (scalar) fields. This phenomenon gives rise to a non-vanishing vacuum energy density of the form $\langle T_{\mu\nu} \rangle = -\langle \rho \rangle g_{\mu\nu}$.

Again our knowledge of the unification of the fields can guide us to determine how the fields in vacuum state may be further organized. Although the high temperatures necessary for unification are physically absent in the vacuum, quantum physics indicates their presence in a virtual way. Due to uncertainty principle, as the dimension of space decreases, the equivalent energy per particle (i.e. the temperature) increases. Also an estimate of the increase in equivalent temperature (energy/particle) can be done from the Heisenberg uncertainty relation. For simplicity let us consider only the x coordinate. If a particle (or a quantum of energy) is confined inside a cubical box a linear size Δx then the minimum uncertainty in the particle's momentum Δp_x is given by the uncertainty principle : $\Delta x \cdot \Delta p_x = h$. A massless relativistic particle with the magnitude of momentum Δp_x will have a kinetic energy E given by, $\Delta p_x = \frac{E}{c}$.

The electroweak unification occurs at an energy (per particle) of 200 GeV. The corresponding linear size of the box should be

$$\Delta x = \frac{h}{\Delta p_x} = \frac{hc}{E} \sim 10^{-16} \text{ cm and then } T = 10^{15} \text{ K.}$$

Similarly, $\Delta x \sim 10^{-30}$ cm for $E = 10^{16}$ GeV and $T = 10^{29}$ K and the planck length $\Delta x \sim 10^{-33}$ cm for $E = 10^{19}$ GeV and $T = 10^{32}$ K

In a similar manner, we can calculate,

$$\Delta x \sim 10^{-36} \text{ cm for } E = 10^{22} \text{ GeV and so on}$$

Note that as $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$ then $E \rightarrow \infty$ and also $T \rightarrow \infty$. According to Alan Guth, the Higgs field, is responsible for spontaneous symmetry breaking of the various stage of unification of the fields.

During symmetry breaking, which separates the strong nuclear field, potential energy of the scalar field is given by

$$\rho \approx \frac{E_{GUT}^4}{(hc)^3} \approx 10^{100} \text{ erg/cm}^3$$

In electroweak unification, the weak fields $W^\pm$, Z^0 and the electromagnetic fields are members of the same mathematical symmetry group $SU(2) \times U(1)$ and the interactions of the strong field belong to the symmetry group $SU(3)$ describing the dynamics of "colour" charges which is known as quantum chromodynamics. The simplest model of this class of theories is based on a mathematical symmetry group $SU(5)$.

The question of why the large energy is not found in practical, the observed vacuum energy is so small in comparison to the scales of particle physics is known as cosmological constant problem. It is generally thought to be easier to imagine an unknown mechanism which would set vacuum parameter exactly to zero and so it can be considered that there exist another unification in the early universe. This class of symmetry group can be expressed mathematically as $SU(11) \supset SU(5) \times SU(6) \times U(1)$. Before the explanation of the groups $SU(11)$, $SU(6)$ and $SU(5)$, we give an example, such as, the change of state of a matter, when it is required latent heat, but this latent heat can not be measured by any instrument but its existence can not be ignored at any cost. As such when in the liquid state the energy of the group $SU(5)$ changes to the ultimate reality of the group of energy $SU(11)$, in the vapour state, there must exists another type of energy group $SU(6)$ like latent heat, its name may be given as 'intelligence', which are responsible for the acceleration of the energy of $SU(5)$, and also the cause for the creation of D.N.A. of the live body etc.

2(a) Intelligence : $SU(6)$. In the transformations under the group $SU(6)$, the basic filed here are the latent energy field and we have

$$U = \exp(-iH), \quad (1)$$

Where H is a 6×6 Hermitian matrix of Zero trace. The matrix H now has 35 independent components. As in the weak interaction $SU(2)$, we have, H has 2×2 Hermitian matrix of zero trace. The most general such matrix is

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} a & b+ic \\ b-ic & -a \end{pmatrix} = a \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix} + b \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + c \begin{pmatrix} 0 & i \\ -i & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Thus, like above, we have 35 matrix charges $I_1, I_2, I_3, \dots, I_{35}$ out of which five matrices are diagonal. Corresponding to this, we have 35 bosons. For want of any specific designation, they are referred to simply as J_k . We expect the participating interactions of the bosons J_k to have comparable strength. The J_k bosons are expected to generate a latent force. This force is believed to be potentially so large that the exotic matter fluid are expected to transfer into the ordinary matter field, and then everything of the universe.

(b) **Super Unified Field : $SU(11)$.** If we wish to unify all three interactions $SU(6)$, $SU(5)$, $U(1)$ in a Super Grand Unification scheme, we could trivially combine the three into a structure

$$SU(6) \times SU(5) \times U(1). \tag{3}$$

From the symmetry breaking of $SU(11)$, we find $SU(6)$ and $SU(5)$ as the subgroup of $SU(11)$, where

$$p(= 5) > 1, n - p(= 11 - 5 = 6) > 1$$

So that

$$SU(n) \supset SU(p) \times SU(n - p) \times U(1)$$

Or, $SU(11) \supset SU(5) \times SU(6) \times U(1)$ (4)

For completeness there also the orthogonal and Symplectic subgroups.

$$SU(11) \supset O(11) \tag{5}$$

$$SU(22) \supset US_p(22) \tag{6}$$

Since the rank of $SU(11)$ is 10 and $U(1)$ is 1, a useful check is that the sum of the ranks of the subgroup $SU(5)$ and $SU(6)$ is less than or equal to the rank of the original group.

Thus, however, it was realized that such a structure (3) can form part of a single large structure denote by $SU(11)$. Again if we go back to equation (1) and apply it to 11×11 matrices, the matrix H has 120 arbitrary constants. Thus there are 120 bosons that now mediate between the different type of energy fields. Of these we already have 24 from $SU(5)$ and 35 from $SU(6)$ and 1 from $U(1)$.

Thus, $120 - (24 + 35 + 1) = 60$ more bosons are needed to make up the list of 120. For want of any specific designation, they are referred to simply as the J bosons. The J bosons are expected to link the participants of $SU(6)$ with $SU(5)$ i.e. $SU(2)$ and $SU(3)$ and $U(1)$. There are emitted and absorbed $\bar{J}$ particles (an anti- J particles). As the energy group $SU(5)$ advanced for unification with $SU(6)$, the strength of weak force gradually increases and the strength of strong force decreases, ultimately the unification occurred at the extreme situation.

It can be expected, that for the symmetry breaking of $SU(11)$, created an amount of positive energy, negative energy and an equivalent amount of latent energy.

3. Cosmology with complex scalar factor. Consider the metric in which the space-time is assumed to be of Robertson-Walker type having a complex scale factor $R + iR_I$, where the scale factor R stands for $(3 + 1)$ -dimensional space-time and iR_I ($= a$) is that for the internal space with dimension D . Avoiding the imaginary term, the line elements can be expressed in the form

$$ds^2 = -N^2(t)dt^2 + R^2(t) \frac{dx^i dx^i}{\left(1 + \frac{kr^2}{4}\right)^2} + a^2(t) \frac{dy^a dy^a}{(1 + k'\rho^2)^2} \quad (7)$$

where $N(t)$ is lapse function, $r^2 = x^i x^i$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$), $\rho^2 = y^a y^a$ ($a = 1, 2, 3, \dots, D$) and $k, k' = 0, \pm 1$, for flat, closed or open type of 4-dimensional universe and D -dimensional space. For simplicity, we assume the internal space to be flat i.e. $k' = 0$. The form of energy-momentum tensor is chosen as

$$T_{AB} = (-\rho, p, p, p, p_D, p_D, \dots, p_D) \quad (8)$$

Now, we examine the case for which the pressure along all the extra-dimensions vanishes, namely $p_D = 0$. In doing so, we are motivated by the brane world scenarios where the matter is to be confined to the 4-dimensional universe, i.e. auxiliary hyper-space, so that all components of T_{AB} is set to zero but the space-time components and it means no matter escapes through the extra dimensions.

We assume the energy-momentum tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ to be that of an exotic χ fluid with the equation of state

$$p_\chi = \left(\frac{m}{3} - 1\right) \rho_\chi \tag{9}$$

Where p_χ and ρ_χ are the pressure and density of the fluid, respectively and the parameter m is restricted to the range $0 \leq m \leq 2$ so that there is violation of strong energy condition and the universe experiences accelerated expansion.

The scalar curvature corresponding to the metric (7) has the expression

$$R = \frac{-6RR_I N \ddot{R} + 6RR_I \dot{N} \dot{R} - 2R^2 \ddot{R}_I N + 2R^2 \dot{N} \dot{R}_I - 2R_I N^3 k + R_I N^3 k^2 r^2 - 6R_I N \dot{R}^2 - 6R \dot{R} \dot{R}_I N}{R^2 N^3 R_I} \tag{10}$$

Now substituting it into the dimensionally extended Einstein-Hilbert action (without higher dimensional cosmological term) including a matter term indicating the above mentioned exotic fluid the effective Lagrangian becomes

$$L = i^D \left[\frac{1}{2N} RR_I^D \dot{R}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12N} RR_I^{D-2} \dot{R}_I^2 + \frac{D}{2N} R^2 R_I^{D-1} \dot{R} \dot{R}_I - \frac{1}{2} k N R R_I^D + \frac{1}{6} N \rho_\chi R^3 R_I^D \right] \tag{11}$$

where dot represents the derivative with respect to t . We shall show an equivalence between ($k = 1$) and ($k = 0$) universes which are favored by observations. The continuity equation, by using the contracted Bianchi identity in $(4 + D)$ dimensions, namely

$$\nabla_M^{G^{MN}} = \nabla_M^{T^{MN}} = 0 \tag{12}$$

together with the assumption that the matter is confined to $(3 + 1)$ dimensional space-time gives $\nabla_i T^{ij} = 0$

$$\text{i.e. } \dot{\rho}_\chi R + 3(p_\chi + \rho_\chi) \dot{R} = 0 \tag{13}$$

Using (9) into the continuity equation (13), the energy density in a closed ($k = 1$) Friedmann-Robertson-Walker universe is

$$\rho_\chi(R) = \rho_\chi(R_0) \left(\frac{R_0}{R}\right)^m \tag{14}$$

where R_0 is the value of R at an arbitrary reference time t_0 .

Again, if we believe that the cosmological term plays an important role in vacuum energy density, then we may the cosmological term as

$$\Lambda \equiv \rho_\chi(R).$$

$$\text{i.e. } L = i^D \left[\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{2N} R R_I^D \dot{R}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12N} R^3 R_I^{D-2} \dot{R}_I^2 + \frac{D}{2N} R^2 R_I^{D-1} \dot{R} \dot{R}_I \\ & - \frac{1}{2} N R R_I^D + \frac{1}{6} N \Lambda R^3 R_I^D \end{aligned} \right] \quad (15)$$

with

$$\Lambda(R) = \Lambda(R_0) \left(\frac{R_0}{R} \right)^m \quad (16)$$

Taking $m = 2$ and $\Lambda(R_0) R_0^2 = 3$

We have

$$\Lambda(R) = \frac{3}{R^2} \quad (17)$$

The lapse function $N(t)$, is an arbitrary function of time due to the fact that Einstein's general relativity is a reparametrization invariant theory. We therefore, take the gauge

$$N(t) = R^3(t) R_I^D(t)_{i^D}, \quad (18)$$

and then Lagrangian (15) becomes

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\dot{R}^2}{R^2} + \frac{D(D-1)}{12} \frac{\dot{R}_I^2}{R_I^2} + \frac{D}{2} \frac{\dot{R} \dot{R}_I}{R R_I} \quad (19)$$

We now define the new variables

$$X = \log R, \quad Y = \log R_I \quad (20)$$

Then the equation (19) becomes

$$L = \frac{1}{2} \dot{X}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12} \dot{Y}^2 + \frac{D}{2} \dot{X} \dot{Y} \quad (21)$$

The equation of motion are obtained

$$\ddot{X} + \frac{D}{2} \ddot{Y} = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$\ddot{X} + \frac{D-1}{3} \ddot{Y} = 0 \quad (23)$$

Solving equations (22) and (23) we get,

$$\ddot{X} = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$\text{and } \ddot{Y} = 0 \quad (25)$$

4. **Solution of Einstein equations in complex field.** The most general line element satisfying the Weyl postulate and the cosmological principle is given by

$$ds^2 = c^2 dt^2 - S^2(t) \left[\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) \right] \quad (26)$$

where 3-space $t=\text{constant}$ are Euclidean for $k = 0$, closed with positive curvature $k = +1$ and open with negative curvature for $k = -1$

We use the above metric to compute the Einstein tensor and thereby formulate the Einstein field equation as

$$2\frac{\ddot{S}}{S} + \frac{\dot{S}^2 + kc^2}{S^2} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^2} p \quad (27)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{\dot{S}^2 + kc^2}{S^2} = \frac{8\pi G}{3c^2} \epsilon \quad (28)$$

where as usual p and ϵ are pressure and energy density, respectively.

Now, considering

$$S = R + iR_I \quad (29)$$

We have from (27)

$$2(R + iR_I)(\ddot{R} + i\ddot{R}_I) + (\dot{R} + i\dot{R}_I)^2 + kc^2 = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^2} p(R + iR_I)^2$$

$$\text{i.e., } 2R\ddot{R} - 2R_I\ddot{R}_I + \dot{R}^2 - \dot{R}_I^2 + kc^2 + 2i(R\ddot{R}_I + R_I\ddot{R} + \dot{R}\dot{R}_I)$$

$$= -\frac{8\pi Gp}{c^2}(R^2 - R_I^2) - 2i\frac{8\pi Gp}{c^2}RR_I$$

Separating real and imaginary parts, we get

$$2R\ddot{R} - 2R_I\ddot{R}_I + \dot{R}^2 - \dot{R}_I^2 + kc^2 = -\frac{8\pi Gp}{c^2}(R^2 - R_I^2) \quad (30)$$

$$\text{and } R\ddot{R}_I + R_I\ddot{R} + \dot{R}\dot{R}_I = -\frac{8\pi Gp}{c^2}RR_I$$

$$\text{i.e. } \frac{d^2}{dt^2}(RR_I) = \dot{R}\dot{R}_I - \frac{8\pi Gp}{c^2}RR_I \quad (31)$$

Again, from the equation (28) using $S = R + iR_I$ and separating real and imaginary part, we have

$$\dot{R}^2 - \dot{R}_I^2 = \frac{8\pi G\epsilon}{3c^2}(R^2 - R_I^2) - kc^2 \quad (32)$$

$$\text{and } \dot{R}\dot{R}_I = \frac{8\pi G\epsilon}{3c^2}RR_I \quad (33)$$

combining equations (31) and (33), we get

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2}(RR_I) = \frac{8\pi G}{3c^2}(\varepsilon - 3p)RR_I \quad (34)$$

Also from the Einstein equations (27) and (28) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}[S(\dot{S}^2 + kc^2)] &\equiv \dot{S}[2S\ddot{S} + \dot{S}^2 + kc^2] \\ \text{i.e. } \frac{d}{ds}(\varepsilon S^3) + 3pS^2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (35)$$

Now according to second law of thermodynamics the entropy in a given volume S^3 remain constant as the volume expands adiabatically. Then

$$s = \frac{\varepsilon + p}{T} \quad (36)$$

is the entropy density and we have

$$\frac{d}{dt}(S^3 \cdot s) = \frac{d}{dt} \left[\frac{S^2}{T} (\varepsilon + p) \right] = 0 \quad (37)$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{S^3}{T} (p + \varepsilon) = \sigma \quad (\text{constant}) \quad (38)$$

Thus using (29), the equation (38) becomes

$$\frac{\sigma T}{p + \varepsilon} = (R + iR_I)^3 = (R^3 - 3RR_I^2) + i(3R^2R_I - R_I^3)$$

Separating real and imaginary part, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\sigma T}{p + \varepsilon} &= R^3 - 3RR_I^2 \quad \text{and} \quad R_I^3 - 3R_I R^2 = 0 \\ \text{i.e. } R_I &= \pm\sqrt{3}R \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

So we have

$$p + \varepsilon = -\frac{\sigma T}{8} \frac{1}{R^3} \quad (40)$$

Using the equation of state (9), ε is given by

$$\varepsilon = \frac{3c^2}{3 - 3c^2 - m} \cdot \frac{1}{8} \cdot \frac{\sigma T}{R^3} \quad (\because \varepsilon = \rho c^2) \quad (41)$$

Then

$$\varepsilon - 3p = \frac{3}{8} \frac{c^2 - m + 3}{3 - 3c^2 - m} \cdot \frac{\sigma T}{R^3} \quad (42)$$

We have from equations (34) using (39) and (42)

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(2R \frac{dR}{dt} \right) = \frac{A}{R} \tag{43}$$

where $A = \frac{\pi G}{c^2} \left(\frac{c^2 - m + 3}{3 - 3c^2 - m} \right) \sigma T$, a constant with respect to time 't'.

Now, integrating the above relation we get

$$(AR + B)^{1/2}(AR - 2B) = \pm \frac{3A^2t}{2} + \frac{3AC}{2} \tag{44}$$

where B and C are integration constants.

Now, we consider, at $t = 0$, the planck time, $R(0) = R_I(0) = \ell_p$.

Then from the above equation we get $2(A\ell_p + B)^{1/2}(A\ell_p - 2B) = 3AC$

Therefore

$$t = \pm \frac{2}{3A^2} \left[(AR + B)^{1/2}(AR - 2B) - (A\ell_p + B)^{1/2}(A\ell_p - 2B) \right] \tag{45}$$

From the above equation, we get calculate the exact time, when $SU(11)$ breaks into $SU(6)$, $SU(5)$. That means when the actual vacuum energy breaks into positive energy, negative energy and latent energy.

The solutions for X and Y from equation (24) and (25) are

$$\begin{aligned} X &= At + \gamma, & Y &= Bt + \delta \\ \therefore R(t) &= A'e^{\alpha t} & \text{and} & R_I(t) = B'e^{\beta t} \end{aligned}$$

where the constants A, B, γ and δ or A', B', α & β should be obtained from the initial conditions.

Consider the size of all spatial dimensions be the same at $t = 0$ and assumed that this size would be the planck size ℓ_p in accordance with quantum cosmological considerations.

So we take

$$R(0) = R_I(0) = \ell_p$$

so that

$$A' = B' = \ell_p.$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} R(t) &= \ell_p e^{\alpha t} \\ \text{and } R_I(t) &= \ell_p e^{\beta t} \end{aligned}$$

It is important to note that the constants α , β are not independent and a relation may be obtained between them. This is done by imposing the zero energy condition $H = 0$ which is the well-known result in cosmology due to the existence of arbitrary lapse function $N(t)$ in the theory. The Hamiltonian constraint is obtained through the Legendre transformation of the Lagrangian (21)

$$H = \frac{1}{2}\dot{X}^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12}\dot{Y}^2 + \frac{D}{2}\dot{X}\dot{Y} = 0$$

$$\text{i.e., } H = \frac{1}{2}\alpha^2 + \frac{D(D-1)}{12}\beta^2 + \frac{D}{2}\alpha\beta = 0 \quad (46)$$

This constraint is satisfied only for $\alpha \leq 0, \beta \geq 0$ or $\alpha \geq 0, \beta \leq 0$.

To find α, β , we first obtained the Hubble parameter for $R(t)$. Again, $H_I = \frac{\dot{R}_I}{R_I} = \beta$ and the Hubble parameter $H_R = \frac{\dot{R}}{R} = \alpha$ by which the constant α is fixed.

$$\therefore R(t) = \ell_p e^{H_R t}, \quad R_I(t) = \ell_p e^{-H_I t} \quad (47)$$

for $D = 1$ also, if $\alpha \neq 0$, then $\alpha = -\beta$ or $\alpha + \beta = 0$, or $\dot{X} + \dot{Y} = 0$, or $X + Y = \text{constant}$, or $\log R + \log R_I = \text{constant}$, $\therefore RR_I = \text{constant}$. Substitute the value of $R(t)$ from (47) in equation (45) we get,

$$t = \pm \frac{2}{3A^2} \left[(A\ell_p e^{H_R t} + B)^{1/2} (A\ell_p e^{H_R t} - 2B) - (A\ell_p + B)^{1/2} (A\ell_p - 2B) \right] \quad (48)$$

Again, for $D \neq 1$, then either $\alpha = 0$ or $\beta = 0$

$$\therefore \dot{X} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \dot{Y} = 0.$$

$$\therefore X = \text{constant}, \quad Y = \text{constant}.$$

$$R = R_I = \ell_p \quad \text{a time independent scale factor}$$

Therefore,

for $D > 1$,

$$\alpha_{\pm} = \frac{D\beta}{2} \left[-1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right)} \right],$$

$$\text{and } H_{R\pm} = \frac{DH_I}{2} \left[-1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D} \right)} \right]$$

So

$$R_I(t) = \ell_p e^{H_I t} \quad (49)$$

$$R_{\pm}(t) = \ell_p e^{\frac{DH_I t}{2}} \left[-1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D}\right)} \right] \quad (50)$$

and $R(t) = \ell_p e^{H_R t} \quad (51)$

$$R_{I_{\pm}}(t) = \ell_p e^{\frac{2H_R t}{D}} \left[-1 \pm \sqrt{1 - \frac{2}{3} \left(1 - \frac{1}{D}\right)} \right]^{-1} \quad (52)$$

Substituting (49), (50), (51), (52) in (45), we also get an equation of time t , by solving this, we get the exact value of the time. It is seen that the time is dependent on the extra-Dimensions D . It is easy to show that the Lagrangian (21) (or the equations of motions) is invariant under the transformation

$$R \rightarrow R^{-1}, \quad R_I \rightarrow R_I^{-1} \quad (53)$$

Which is consistent with the time reversal $t \rightarrow -t$

For the special case, when $D = 3$, both the Lagrangian (21) and the Hamiltonian (46) are invariant under the transformation

$$R \rightarrow R_I, \quad R_I \rightarrow R.$$

Therefore, we have dynamical symmetry between R and R_I , namely $R_I \leftrightarrow R$. In this case there is no distinction between R_I and R to single out one of them as the real scale factor of the universe. Because $k' = 0$ and according to (19), we assume the $4D$ universe with $k, \Lambda \neq 0$ to be equivalent to the one in which $k = \Lambda = 0$. Therefore both have the same topology S^3 .

5. Quantum cosmology over complex space. Quantum cosmology explain an appropriate quantum mechanical description of the universe, which was introduced and developed by DeWitt. In quantum cosmology the universe, as a whole is treated quantum mechanically and is described by a single wave function, $\psi(h_{ij}, \phi)$ defined on a manifold (super space) of all possible three geometries and all matter field configurations. The wave function $\psi(h_{ij}, \phi)$ has no explicit time dependence due to the fact that there is no real time parameter external to the universe. Therefore, there is no Schrödinger wave equation but the operator version of the Hamiltonian constraint of the Dirac canonical quantization procedure, namely vanishing of the variation of the Einstein-Hillbert action S with respect to the arbitrary lapse function N .

Thus

$$H = \frac{\delta S}{\delta N} = 0,$$

which is written as

$$\hat{H}\psi(h_{ij}, \phi) = 0 \quad (54)$$

This equation is known as the Wheeler-DeWitt (WDW) equation. The goal of quantum cosmology by solving the WDW equation over the complex space $(R + iR_I)$ is to understand the origin and evolution of the universe.

In principle, it is very difficult to solve the WDW equation in the super space due to the large number of degrees of freedom. In practice, one has a *freeze out* of all but a finite number of degree of freedom of the gravitational and matter fields. This procedure is known as quantization in mini-super-space, and will be used in the following.

The mini-super-space in our model is two dimensional with gravitational variables X and Y . To obtain the Wheeler-DeWitt equation, in his mini-super-space, we start with the Lagrangian (21). The conjugate momenta corresponding to X and Y are obtained as

$$P_X = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{X}} = \dot{X} + \frac{D}{2} \dot{Y} \quad (55)$$

$$P_Y = \frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{Y}} = \frac{D}{2} \dot{X} + \frac{D(D-1)}{6} \dot{Y} \quad (56)$$

From which we obtain

$$\dot{X} = \frac{6}{D+2} \left[P_X \left(\frac{1-D}{3} \right) + P_Y \right] \quad (57)$$

$$\dot{Y} = \frac{6}{D(D-1)} \left[P_Y \frac{2(1-D)}{D+2} - P_X \frac{D(1-D)}{D+2} \right] \quad (58)$$

Substituting equation (57) and (58) into the Hamiltonian constraint (46) which obtained through the legender transformation of Lagrangian (21) as

$$H = (1-D)P_X^2 - \frac{6}{D}P_Y^2 + 6P_X P_Y = 0 \quad (59)$$

Now, we may use the following quantum mechanical replacements

$$P_X \rightarrow -i \frac{\partial}{\partial X}, \quad P_Y \rightarrow -i \frac{\partial}{\partial Y}$$

and Wheeler-DeWitt equations takes the form

$$\left[(D-1) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial X^2} + \frac{6}{D} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial Y^2} - 6 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \psi(X, Y) = 0 \quad (60)$$

Where $\psi(X, Y)$ is the wave function of the universe in the (X, Y) mini-super-space.

The general solution is

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_D(X, Y) = & \phi_1 \left\{ D(D-1)Y + 3DX + \sqrt{3D^2 + 6DX} \right\} \\ & + \phi_2 \left\{ D(D-1)Y + 3DX - \sqrt{3D^2 + 6DX} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{i.e., } \psi_D(R, R_I) = \phi_1 \left[\log \left\{ R^{3D + \sqrt{3D^2 + 6D}} \cdot R_I^{D(D-1)} \right\} \right] \\ + \phi_2 \left[\log \left\{ R^{3D - \sqrt{3D^2 + 6D}} \cdot R_I^{D(D-1)} \right\} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (61)$$

Now for

$$\psi_D(R, R_I) \leftrightarrow \psi_D(R_I, R)$$

we have

$$3D \pm \sqrt{3D^2 + 6D} = D(D - 1)$$

$$\text{i.e. } D = 1 \text{ or } 6$$

So if $D > 1$ then we must have $D = 6$.

Again, to find another solution of the WDW equation we rewrite (60) as

$$\begin{aligned} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial X} - \left\{ \frac{3}{D-1} - \frac{1}{(D-1)} \sqrt{\frac{3(D+2)}{D}} \right\} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \\ \left[(D-1) \frac{\partial}{\partial X} - \left\{ 3 + \sqrt{\frac{3(D+2)}{D}} \right\} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \psi(X, Y) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (62)$$

Using separation of variables

$$\psi(X, Y) = \phi(X) \cdot \psi(Y), \quad (63)$$

We obtain the following equations

$$\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial X} = \frac{\gamma}{D-1} \phi(X) \quad (64)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial Y} = \frac{\gamma}{3 + \sqrt{\frac{3(D+2)}{D}}} \psi(Y) \quad (65)$$

where we assume $\gamma > 0$.

The solution of equations (64) and (65), are

$$\phi(X) = e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1}} \quad (66)$$

$$\text{and } \psi(Y) = e^{\pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{DY}}{3\sqrt{D} + \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (67)$$

$$\therefore \psi_D^\pm(X, Y) = A^\pm e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1} \pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{DY}}{3\sqrt{D} + \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (68)$$

$$\text{and } \psi_D^\pm(X, Y) = B^\pm e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1} \mp \frac{\gamma \sqrt{DY}}{3\sqrt{D} + \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (69)$$

Also from the equations (62), we have

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial X} - \left\{ \frac{3}{D-1} + \frac{1}{D-1} \sqrt{\frac{3(D+2)}{D}} \right\} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \left[(D-1) \frac{\partial}{\partial X} - \left\{ 3 - \sqrt{\frac{3(D+2)}{D}} \right\} \frac{\partial}{\partial Y} \right] \psi(X, Y) = 0 \quad (70)$$

Using the above process the solutions of the equation (70) are

$$\psi_D^\pm(X, Y) = A^\pm e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1} \pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D} Y}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (71)$$

$$\text{and } \psi_D^\pm(X, Y) = B^\pm e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1} \mp \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D} Y}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (72)$$

Combining (68) and (69) with (71) and (72) we have,

$$\psi_D^\pm(X, Y) = A^\pm e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1} \pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D} Y}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (73)$$

$$\psi_D^\pm(X, Y) = B^\pm e^{\pm \frac{\gamma X}{D-1} \mp \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D} Y}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}}} \quad (74)$$

Where $A^\pm, B^\pm$ are the normalization constant, thus we may write,

$$\psi_D^\pm(R, R_I) = A^\pm R^\pm \frac{\gamma}{D-1} R_I^\pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D}}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}} \quad (75)$$

$$\psi_D^\pm(R, R_I) = B^\pm R^\pm \frac{\gamma}{D-1} R_I^\mp \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D}}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}} \quad (76)$$

Now, for $\psi_D^\pm(R, R_I) \leftrightarrow \psi_D^\pm(R_I, R)$, we have

$$\pm \frac{\gamma}{D-1} = \pm \frac{\gamma \sqrt{D}}{3\sqrt{D} \pm \sqrt{3(D+2)}} \quad [\because \gamma > 0]$$

$$\text{i.e., } D = 1, 6$$

Thus for $D > 1$, i.e., for $D = 6$ there is a change symmetry,

$$\psi_D(R, R_I) \leftrightarrow \psi_D(R_I, R) \text{ Under the change } R_I \leftrightarrow R.$$

6. Concluding Remarks. First we studied the unification of the energy group $SU(5)$ with $SU(6)$ (which may be called a group for intelligence and it may form physically 'Blackhole') to form a special unitary group $SU(11)$. However, if the large percent of the matter sources in the universe would be of dark-energy type (as the present observations strongly recommend) then

one may keep the results here even in the presence of other matter source, keeping in mind that the relevant contribution to the total matter source of the universe is the dark energy. We studied a $(4 + D)$ dimensional classical kaluza-klein cosmology with a Robertson-Walker type metric having complex scale factor $R + iR_I$, by introducing a typical exotic matter with the equation of state

$$p_x = \left(\frac{m}{3} - 1\right) \rho_x$$

And with the consideration of the entropy of the universe. We thus, assume an empty space which is not empty at all. On the contrary, the quantum vacuum is the 'home of nature's infinite dynamism. According to our solution, a singularity is avoided by describing the initial conditions of the universe with quantum effects.

We have also studied the corresponding quantum cosmology, through the Wheeler-DeWitt equation, and obtained the exact solutions.

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